

This paper is published at Journal Discrete Mathematics, Algorithms and Applications
DOI: 10.1142/s1793830922500550
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Minimum constraint removal problem for line segments is NP-hard

Abstract: In the minimum constraint removal (MCR), there is no feasible path to move from a starting point towards the goal, and the minimum constraints should be removed in order to find a collision-free path. It has been proved that MCR problem is NP-hard when constraints have arbitrary shapes or even they are in shape of convex polygons. However, it has a simple linear solution when constraints are lines and the problem is open for other cases yet. In this paper, using a reduction from Subset Sum problem, in three steps, we show that the problem is NP-hard for both weighted and unweighted line segments.

Keywords: Algorithm; computational geometry; line segments; MCR; motion planning.

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